

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Library and Information Services

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Abstract:

Now a day's Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the emerging trend and applications of computing in libraries. The present study explores the potential of AI to bring about transformation in library and information services. Artificial intelligence in libraries being used to improve library and information services, organize collections, personalize user experiences and automate tasks, with potential benefits for cataloging, resource discovery and user support. While it can enhance librarian's capabilities and assist with research, it also presents challenges related to implementation, funding, staff training and the need for responsible ethical guidelines to ensure equitable and private use. The application of Artificial intelligence in library has become pervasive. They include expert systems for book reading, reference services. Today artificial intelligence will greatly improve library and information services and will upgrade the heighten the relevance of libraries in an ever-changing digital age. The present study shows that how important role of artificial intelligence in library and information centers.

Keywords: *Concept of Artificial Intelligence, Library and Information Services, Barriers of implementing AI in Library and Information Centers.*

Introduction:

In 1955 John McCarthy coined the term 'Artificial Intelligence' that's why he is the father of Artificial Intelligence. Basically, AI is a branch of computer science. Most of the computer systems and mobile phones being developed today have AI features and we have probably used them not knowing that they are intelligent machine. Today AI touches most of our daily computing works like Entertainment, Education, Transportation, Sports, libraries etc. Main focus of artificial intelligence is perception, reasoning and action. AI offers many benefits like bridge in time, bridge in space, minimization of efforts, enhanced and immersive user experience in library delivery, maximization of effectiveness in form of improve services delivery, elimination of human errors in library operations. That's why AI is very important for today's libraries.

AI helps the librarian in realizing in the need for an improvement in the library operations and services. AI is transforming libraries by automating routine tasks, enhancing search and discovery through personalized recommendations, improving data analysis for collection development and user engagement. Today's fastest age AI is very useful for any libraries to give fastest and accurate services. AI also aids in library management like data analysis for collection development, digital preservation of materials and automated cataloging. Ultimately AI helps librarians become more efficient and accessible to user needs.

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Library and Information Services:

In enhanced accessibility, effective management, enhanced personalization, efficiency, relevance, effective services

automated services artificial intelligence plays a crucial role. Today's age is fastest age so to give within a time services AI is very necessary. Some of the areas in libraries AI can be used to improve library status. These are as follows.

1. Automatic indexing using AI.
2. In translation service AI can be used.
3. By automatic cataloging AI saves time of library staff.
4. In classification service which is very important part of library AI can be used to save time and efforts.
5. Intelligent document delivery services.
6. In digital preservation process AI can be used.
7. 24/7 virtual assistance AI is very important.
8. In collection management.
9. Automated reference services.
10. Advanced research support.
11. For improvement in accessibility AI can be used.
12. Advanced security systems.

Artificial intelligence systems will improve the performance of library services and reduce the rate of human errors and perform task faster than human being. Hence AI have great potential for improve status of library and information services. AI provides 24/7 assistance and creates more efficient, accessible for users and library staff. AI is an extensively used technology in library that can transform the best services in the age of Information Technology.

Barriers of Implementing AI in Library and Information Centers:

There are number of barriers to the implementation of AI in library and information centers. These includes Lack of finance, Staff skills, Data privacy and security, Lack of space, Lack of infrastructure etc. few of main is given below.

1. Implementation costs: The main obstacles of implementing AI are funding for infrastructure, software and maintenance. It requires high system development.

2. Lack of skilled staff: Library staff require new technical skills and ongoing professional development to effectively utilize and manage AI tools, creating a skills gap. Library staff also require training programme for updating of knowledge.

3. Data privacy: Here is another one drawback of implementation of AI. Libraries must navigate the complex responsibilities of managing large volumes of user data, ensuring compliance with privacy regulation and safe guarding sensitive information.

Lack of space, lack of power supply, lack of internet connectivity etc. there are many barriers in implementing AI in library and information centers.

Conclusion:

Present age is fastest and digital age. So, to improve status of libraries, to give fast services libraries must have implement new technologies like AI. AI has massive potential advantages like user structured information environment, smart document delivery service, intelligent gateways to online sources etc. AI can help library staff discover new and emerging trends like robotics, RFID etc. With these new emerging technologies libraries improve their status. So, in this way role of AI in library and information centers are very important for digitization of libraries. In short, we can say that AI is boon for library and information centers. Thus, AI holds great potential for library and information centers.

References:

1. [http:// online_courses.Swayamz.ac.in/CeC23_Ib03/announcements](http://online_courses.Swayamz.ac.in/CeC23_Ib03/announcements)
2. [http://en.Wikipedia.org/Wiki/Artificial_intelligence.](http://en.Wikipedia.org/Wiki/Artificial_intelligence)